

Stability Constants of Copper(II) Chelates with some Substituted 1,3-Propanediones at 0.1M Ionic Strength Potentiometrically

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Metal-ligand stability constants of dicarboxylic acids (succinic, itaconic, adipic and malonic) with transition metal ions have been determined in aqueous medium by many workers¹. Shelke and Jahagirdar² studied equilibrium constants of UO_2^{++} and Cu^{II} with dicarboxylic acids in dioxane-water mixtures. Narwade *et al.*³ investigated the interaction of Fe^{III} with substituted chalcones at 0.1 M ionic strength potentiometrically. Gudadhe *et al.*⁴ determined the stability constants of Cu^{II} with substituted isoxazolines in 70% dioxane-water mixture. The interaction between Cu^{II} chelates with 2-hydroxyaromatic ketones and aralkylmonoamines was studied by Nath and Bhatnagar⁵. The stability constant values of transition metal ion complexes with 1,3-propanediones are still lacking. It was therefore thought worthwhile to study the chelating properties of substituted 1,3-propanediones potentiometrically.

In the present investigation the interaction of Cu^{II} with 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-phenyl-1,3-propanedione, 1-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-3-phenyl-1,3-propanedione and 1-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-3-(4'-methoxy)phenyl-1,3-propanedione has been investigated potentiometrically in 70% dioxane-water mixture at 0.1 M ionic strength.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand stability constants : Substituted 1,3-propanediones may be considered as monobasic acids having only one replaceable H^+ ion from phenolic OH group and can, therefore, be represented as HL. It is observed from the titration curves that the ligand curves start deviation from the free acid (HClO_4) curves at about pH 6.5. The deviation increased continuously upto pH 10.0. It indicates that OH group starts to dissociate at about pH 6.5 and complete its dissociation at about pH 10.0.

The proton-ligand formation numbers ($\bar{n}_A$) were calculated by Irving and Rossotti's expression⁶. The $\text{p}K'$ values were estimated from formation curves ($\bar{n}_A$ vs pH) by noting the pH at which $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$. The accurate values of pH were determined by pointwise calculations. It is seen that the $\text{p}K$ values decrease from ligand no. 1 to 3. It may be due to increasing electron-releasing tendencies of the CH_3 and OCH_3 groups.

TABLE I—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF 1,3-SUBSTITUTED-PROPANEDIONES

Ionic strength = 0.1 M

Sl. no.	System	$\text{p}K'$
1.	1-(2-Hydroxyphenyl)-3-phenyl-1,3-propanedione	8.95
2.	1-(2-Hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-3-phenyl-1,3-propanedione	8.50
3.	1-(2-Hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-3-(4'-methoxy)-phenyl-1,3-propanedione	6.90

Precision of experimentally determined pH values : The precision of the experimental pH values was examined by determination of the $\text{p}K'$ values of the ligand from two sets of potentiometric titrations. All the experimental conditions except the concentrations of the ligands and sodium hydroxide were kept identical for the two sets. The proton-ligand formation number $\bar{n}_A$ at various values, obtained from the two sets for ligand no. 1 are presented in Table 2. The values of $\bar{n}_A$ at a particular pH and the standard deviation of these values are also calculated by using an expression,

$$\sigma = \left[\frac{\sum (\Delta \bar{n}_A)^2}{n'-1} \right]^{1/2}$$

where n' is the number of observations.

Metal-ligand stability constants : The stepwise formation constants of the Cu^{II} complexes with the above substituted 1,3-propanediones were determined by employing Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti.

The formation of chelate between Cu^{II} and dif-

ferent substituted 1,3-propanediones was indicated by (i) the significant departure, starting at pH 4.0, of the metal complex titration curve from the ligand curve and (ii) the change in colour from dirty brown to light brown and finally to deep brown as pH was raised from 4.0 to 7.0. It showed that the commencement of complex formation is in pH range 4.0–7.0.

TABLE 2—STANDARD DEVIATION OF 1-(2-HYDROXYPHENYL)-3-PHENYL-1,3-PROPANEDIONE

Ionic strength = 0.1 M

pH	$\bar{n}_A$		$\Delta\bar{n}_A$
	Expt.	Calcd.	
7.2	0.997 2	0.991 2	+ 0.006 2
7.4	0.983 1	0.985 3	- 0.002 2
7.6	0.947 1	0.947 9	- 0.000 8
7.8	0.894 3	0.899 1	- 0.004 8
8.0	0.841 5	0.850 0	- 0.008 5
8.2	0.788 7	0.781 3	+ 0.007 4
8.4	0.735 8	0.731 9	+ 0.003 8
8.6	0.630 2	0.644 2	- 0.014 0
8.8	0.524 2	0.524 9	- 0.000 7
9.0	0.415 8	0.416 0	- 0.000 2
9.2	0.313 3	0.300 9	+ 0.002 4
9.4	0.207 6	0.211 1	+ 0.003 5
9.6	0.198 1	0.189 9	+ 0.008 2
9.8	0.102 8	0.110 3	- 0.007 5

$\sigma = 6.48 \times 10^{-3}$

While calculating $\bar{n}$ (metal-ligand formation number) and pL , the concentrations were corrected for changes in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titrations. A series of values were calculated using the equation of Van-Uitert and Haas⁷. The log K values were directly read from the formation curves ($\bar{n}$ vs pL) using half-integral method.

The most accurate values were calculated by least-square method. The values of $\log K$ ($\log K_1 - \log K_2$) and $\log K_1 / \log K_2$ are presented in Table 3. It is observed that the values of K ($\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) decreased due to the effect of electron-releasing groups (CH_3 and OCH_3). One would expect a larger difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values in such ligands because of possible steric hindrance to the linking of the secondary ligand to the metal ion. The smaller difference may be due to *trans*-structure. The results (Table 3) show that the ratio of $\log K_1 / \log K_2$ is positive in all the cases because 1 : 1 complex formation occurs at low pH and hence first metal-ligand stability constant ($\log K_1$) is greater than the second metal-ligand stability constant ($\log K_2$) of the complex. Separation factors between first and second formation constants are well within the expected range.

Validity of $\log K = apK' + b$ relation: The linear relationship has been found out by some workers⁸ to hold for transition metal complexes of a series of closely related ligands. The same relation has been studied in the present investigation to verify the series of transition metal complexes. Similar plots of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ vs pK' (figures not shown) show satisfactory linear relationship giving slope values of 1.10 and 1.08 respectively. The slope value of the above relation is near about unity, which shows that the partial molar free energies of the metal-ligand and proton-ligand complexes exactly compensate each other. The same study has been performed by Narwade and Sawalakhe⁹.

TABLE 3—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE Cu^{II} COMPLEXES

Ionic strength = 0.1 M

Sl. no.	System	Constants		$(\log K_1 - \log K_2)$	$\log K_1 / \log K_2$
		$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$		
1	Cu^{II} -1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-phenyl-1,3-propanedione	9.25	8.35	0.90	1.11
2	Cu^{II} -1-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-3-phenyl-1,3-propanedione	8.55	7.60	0.95	1.13
3	Cu^{II} -1-(2-hydroxy-5-methoxyphenyl)-3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1,3-propanedione	7.05	6.05	1.00	1.25

Experimental

Copper nitrate (AnalaR) was dissolved in perchloric acid and its concentration was estimated by standard procedure¹⁰. Substituted 1,3-propanediones were prepared by Baker-Venkatraman transformation of the appropriate 2-aryloxyacetophenone as reported in literature¹¹. As substituted-1,3-propanediones are insoluble in water, dioxane-water (70%, v/v) was used as a solvent. The other solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. 1,4-Dioxane was purified by standard method¹⁰ and its purity was checked by potassium iodide. Measurements of pH were carried out with an Elico LI-10 pH meter (accuracy ± 0.05 unit) using glass and calomel electrodes at $27 \pm 0.10^\circ$. The B -values (pH meter readings in 70% dioxane-water mixture) were converted to hydrogen ion concentration values by applying the correlations proposed by Van Uitert and Haas⁷. The ionic strength

NOTE

of solution was maintained constant ($\mu = 0.1M$) by adding an appropriate amount of 1 M NaClO₄ solution. The overall ionic strength of the solution was calculated by the expression,

$$\mu = \frac{1}{2} \sum C_i Z_i^2$$

The contribution of the other ions in addition to Na⁺ and ClO₄⁻ were also taken into consideration.

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